
Assessing the Influence of Influencer Leadership, Digital Transformation and Social Climate on Improving Teacher Achievement in Building Excellent Madrasahs

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ABSTRACT: Achievement in the world of education is identical to the achievement of student learning outcomes in academic or non-academic fields. The focus of education tends to be on output. It turns out that outstanding teachers are able to become an important element as producers of quality generations who are competitive at the global level and successful in their future lives. The focus of the study aims to assess how much influence influencer leadership, digital transformation and social climate have on improving teacher achievement in building superior madrasahs. This study uses a descriptive quantitative approach with data analysis techniques using Smart-PLS to measure variables that influence and influence each other. The number of respondents in the study was 124 private madrasah teachers in Malang Regency with a Likert scale measurement of 1-5. The analysis of Cronbach's alpha values as a whole and explaining the construct is internally consistent and reliable in this test. The results of the study showed that: (1) There is a significant influence between influencer leadership and improving teacher achievement; (2) there is a significant influence between digital transformation and improving teacher achievement and (3) there is no significant influence between social climate and improving teacher achievement. Predictively, researchers see that psychological factors in the form of self-efficacy have a greater influence than social climate in terms of improving teacher achievement. to the independent variable.

KEYWORDS: Influencer Leadership, Digital Transformation, Social Climate, Teacher Achievement, Excellent Madrasah

INTRODUCTION

Teachers have a central role in advancing and improving the quality of education of a nation. Advanced educational institutions tend to have competent, progressive-thinking and accomplished teachers. Teachers today are not enough with professionals, because professional status is limited to administrative fulfillment to increase welfare levels without being accompanied by the emergence of creativity and increased competence that is comprehensive in it. Competent teachers are expected to be able to carry out the learning process correctly, creatively and innovatively so as to encourage students to be more motivated, understand, and implement it in everyday life. The categorization of professional teachers can also be seen from the various achievements they have both individually and together. In the Law on Teachers and Lecturers No. 20 of 2009, there are four basic competencies that must be possessed by teachers, namely personality, pedagogical, professional and social competencies. In the context of madrasah education in Indonesia, increasing achievement is still focused on the achievement of academic grades for students and their graduates. Our education is not too focused on how to improve teacher achievement. This is important to pay attention to because teachers are the ones who will form a quality and highly competitive generation at the global level with success in life in the world and the hereafter. (Saleh, 2024) With the provision of integrated knowledge provided by teachers, it is hoped that future graduates will be resilient in facing all changes in accordance with the progress of the times.

In fact, the current government has not really focused on improving the quality and achievement of teachers along with technological advances in the digital era. Not enough with better quality education, the importance of forming character, social skills and leadership is increasingly recognized and needed by the world of education in general, in which there are important agents for the progress of the nation, namely students and learners, both of whom interact and are involved in building advanced and quality education. Quality education can encourage the development of holistic personality capacity in society to face changes in the era of the 21st century which is called the digital era. Leaders of educational institutions in this era must be ready for all environmental changes and be digitally competent. The phenomenon of influencer leaders is one of the emergence of new leadership styles that can be applied in educational institutions, especially madrasahs. Influencer leaders are individuals who have great influence in a

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community, organization or industry, especially through social media platforms. They often have the ability to influence the opinions, behaviors, and decisions of others, both in business, political, and social contexts.

The rapid development of digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence, big data, cloud computing, Blockchain, and industrial internet, is shifting the traditional economy into a digital and intelligent economy which is an important mechanism for organizations to achieve innovation breakthroughs and sustainable development. Currently, in Indonesia there are still 19% of educational units that have difficulty getting internet access. Of that number, as many as 42,159 schools still do not have internet access. Meanwhile, 81% or as many as 175,356 schools are already connected to the internet. That matter will be one of the inhibiting factors for the learning process in this digital era. Roger (2016), said that in addition to technology-related issues, digital transformation is also related to strategies where leadership or managers must be able to find ways to create innovations and new business models and also be able to optimize customer needs and experiences. (Rogers, 2016) In line with this opinion, Weller et al (2013) also stated that digital transformation allows organizations to sustain themselves in an era of rapid change; however, this transformation still requires strategic direction. According to Lee et al (2013), leaders must view risk and uncertainty as natural business elements and must prepare for all possible future scenarios aggressively and pre-emptively. Capable leaders of educational institutions are able to overcome further risks and challenges. Not only that, madrasahs as Islamic educational institutions aspire to achieve comprehensive educational goals, they also strive through various academic and non-academic programs that have been designed in a balanced manner in the P5RA curriculum (Pancasila-Rahmatan Lilalamin Student Profile Strengthening Project). Not enough with the curriculum, the condition of the learning environment, the social environment and the quality of teachers are also important highlights for building superior madrasahs today. Madrasahs today should be able to become one of the educational facilities that can provide the best experience for their students so that a sense of love and pride grows in the madrasah where they study. The condition of the learning environment experienced by students while studying can affect almost all aspects for optimizing student functions in madrasahs. The concept of comfort, satisfaction and happiness will be able to improve students' welfare, so that students can consciously follow the learning process well and enjoyably. From the results of the Scientific research ddk. (Scientific, 2023) quantitatively obtained that there is a significant influence between visionary leadership and entrepreneurial competence of the madrasah principal on the formation of school well-being at MTs. Wahid Hasyim 02 Dau with odds ratio values of 4.610 and 5.015 greater than the lowest category. The conclusion of the study states that an optimally developed leadership style can affect the level of student welfare. Similar things also provide an overview of the importance of the madrasah principal's strategy in managing his institution. From the results of Wakhid Nuryanto's research which analyzed the strategic plan and strategic steps of the Madrasah Principal in increasing the interest of prospective students, it turned out to have a positive impact and was significantly correlated with the competitive competition of educational institutions. (Wahid Nuryanto, 2020) In Maxwell's research, School climate is a major factor in explaining learning and academic achievement. But there is still little discussion of the impact of staff and student perceptions of school climate can raise the question of whether the experience of the community, especially staff, can affect student achievement. In addition, the social identity approach, school identification is investigated as a possible psychological mechanism to explain the relationship between school climate and achievement which results in a positive effect (Maxwell, 2017). The three studies can be a picture that the role of leaders, technological advances and student learning environments can have an impact on the success of the entire community in the process of improving the quality of education. The formation of a conducive learning atmosphere should be created in the school environment. This can have an impact on the conduciveness of the school climate which influences the attitudes and actions of the entire school community.

The leadership approach that is considered appropriate at this time is an approach that prioritizes collaboration, joint decision-making, and instilling a positive school culture and not being left behind by technological advances. (Cruikshank, 2017) Influencer leaders are seen as catalysts for change that can encourage an environment with high creativity, so that they can carve out various achievements for their teachers and students. This is where the label of superior madrasah began. Superior madrasahs focus on quality education, good management, and a supportive community. (Fani Yantik, 2022) Comprehensive curriculum, innovative teaching strategies, and evaluation to achieve the potential of teachers and students Building the excellence of madrasahs can provide important insights for improving the quality of Islamic educational institutions which will later affect the improvement of the quality of education in Indonesia. This is in accordance with the opinion of Stewart and Marshall, that effective management can function to ensure that madrasahs are able to provide high and best standards of educational services for all of their communities. (Maxwell, 2017)

From the description above, it is considered important for the author to conduct further research with three hypothesis formulations, namely (1) H₁ Influencer Leadership will have a positive effect on increasing teacher achievement (2) H₂ Digital transformation will have a positive effect on increasing teacher achievement and (3) H₃ Social Climate will have a positive effect on increasing teacher achievement. By increasing teacher achievement in each educational unit, it will be easier to build superior madrasahs. In previous studies, the focus of the research was on student achievement and student learning outcomes. This research was conducted at a junior high school, namely a Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs) in Malang Regency, a total of 124 under the guidance of Maarif Educational Institution PCNU Malang Regency.

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RESEARCH METHODS

This study was designed with a descriptive quantitative approach using a simple random sampling method. Data collection techniques were obtained from learners and teachers of private MTs in Malang Regency, namely MTs.S Almaarif 01 Singosari, MTs.S NU Pakis, MTs.S Ahmad Yani Jabung, MTs.S Darun Najah Karangploso and MTs.S Nurul Huda Ngajum. The researcher selected 150 samples consisting of students and learners. A total of 124 respondents have filled out the questionnaire online via Google Forms. Data was collected for two weeks with limited identities and only known to the researcher. Of the total 150 questionnaires distributed, 124 responses were received well, while the rest were incomplete and not collected within the specified time limit.

The instrument in the questionnaire uses a 1-5 likerts scale with the number of statements adjusted to the needs of the study, amounting to 45 statements. In compiling the instrument, the researcher followed the scientific principles for developing the questionnaire (Cohen, J, 1988). First, determine the indicators for each variable X which are then made into statements according to the aspects as an instrument that will be distributed and in line with the research objectives. Second, the questionnaire was sent further to three experts in similar subject areas to be corrected and get input or improvements. The experts suggested minor changes to the statement items to improve clarity. Finally, the author conducted a pilot study by taking 20 samples to check the validity of the content and its completeness. It was found that respondents did not request any changes to the final version of the questionnaire.

RESULTS

A. Statistical Measurement

The size in this study statistically uses the Cronbach's alpha (α) value which is a measure of reliability and is generally used to measure the amount of random measurement error present in the sum or average score produced by a multi-item measurement scale. The use of the methodology also warns that α is not an optimal measure of reliability (Hayes, A & Coutts, 2020). Although the use of Cronbach's alpha values is considered to have the disadvantage of relying less on empirical studies, overall the Cronbach's alpha value can be the basis for measuring variables in research (McNeish, D. 2017). The value of the Samrt-PLS output is presented in the figure below with an overall value greater than 0.7. This value can be interpreted that the constructs are internally consistent and reliable. Reliability metrics can also be accessed using Rho A. Rho Value A value greater than or equal to 0.7 is also considered a good measure of reliability.

Figure 1. Smart-PLS output results showing correlation and its influence.

B. Validity Test

Convergent validity measures how well multiple items assess the same construct (Fornell and Bookstein, 1982; Barclay et al., 1995). A composite reliability (CR) value of 0.7 or higher indicates a high level of internal consistency reliability (Bagozzi and Yi, 1988; Hair et al., 2010). All constructs had CR values greater than 0.7 (see Output Figure) Discriminant Validity The independence of constructs from one another is what is meant by the term “discriminant validity.” Low correlations between the target construct being measured and other constructs in the study are indicative of discriminant validity (Cheung and Lee, 2010; Hair et al., 2010). This indicates that the measures are derived from the construct itself (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). This is the squared correlation between the construct and the variance taken for the construct in the partial least squares analysis (Komiak et al., 2004; Henseler and Chin, 2010). Therefore, it can be said that the measurement model used in this study is adequate (Henseler and Chin, 2010).

C. R Square Value

Table 1. R Square and R² values

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Teacher Achievement	0.542	0.531

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From Table 1. Explains the R Square value on the variance in endogenous variables explained by exogenous variables. From the results obtained, it can be seen that the R Square value is 0.542 and 0.531, which means that the endogenous latent variable is in the moderate category. In this study, it can be said that teacher achievement is influenced by the variables of influencer leadership, digital transformation and social climate by 54.2%. This value is in the moderate category. This categorization is in accordance with the recommendations of Hair et al. (2011) that the R2 value for endogenous latent variables is 0.75 (substantial), 0.5 (moderate) and 0.25 (weak).

D. Hypothesis Testing

Table 2. P-Value Test and T-Test

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Social Climate -> Teacher Achievement	0.136	0.144	0.106	1,278	0.202
Influencer Leadership -> Teacher Achievement	0.458	0.461	0.100	4,568	0,000
Digital Transformation -> Teacher Achievement	0.224	0.217	0.108	2,082	0.038

The analysis in Table 2 is a combination to test the direct influence of the variables of influencer leadership, digital transformation and social climate on teacher achievement in forming superior madrasahs. In Table 2, the correlation analysis that explains the significance value of the dependent variable on the independent variables in the study, namely Influencer Leadership (STDEV 0.100, T 4.568, $p < 0.01$) and Digital Transformation (STDEV 0.008, T 2.082, $p < 0.05$). However, the social climate variable (STDEV 0.106, T 5 1.278, $p > 0.05$) does not show a significant relationship with teacher achievement in forming superior madrasahs.

DISCUSSION

Since the emergence of COVID-19, educational institutions have struggled to continue implementing the education process comprehensively and transformatively. The online learning process has triggered and spurred many people to think creatively and innovatively in implementing the education process. Leaders must be able to make the right decisions in carrying out the education process that directly involves students (Gurukkal, 2020; Dubey and Sahu, 2021, 2022, 2022a; Nyathi and Sibanda, 2022). The changes in learning systems and patterns have presented many challenges for all educational institutions, especially madrasahs. As time goes by and the era shifts from the birth of the millennial generation, generation Z, and generation alpha, in 2025 the beta generation will begin to emerge as the first generation of changing times. Education actors need to understand how education patterns must be applied to future generations so that the role of education is not only a formality but can shape the character of a generation of the nation that is "smart and dignified".

Educational institutions, especially madrasahs, must be able to become agencies in realizing a society that grows and develops sustainably. This study attempts to test the influence of internal factors of the Institution (Influencer leadership, digital transformation and social climate) on improving teacher achievement in forming superior madrasahs. The results of H1 and H2 provide answers that the proposed hypothesis can be accepted positively. The results of the study obtained that influencer leadership shows consistency and is positive because the role of leaders as directors and decision makers in determining policies can increase teacher motivation to further hone their competencies so that they have competitiveness in achieving positively. Learning experiences that experience changes towards a more advanced direction in the digital era can provide changes in the organizational culture of the Institution.

Digital transformation developed by an institution and involving all components of the institution can have a positive effect on the achievements of the entire community, both teacher and student achievements. This is in accordance with previous research that the existence of technology cannot be ignored in the world of education, so the role of digital transformation in madrasahs is very important, because with technology the learning process will be easier, more interesting and more enjoyable. Other similar studies (Piccoli et al., 2001; Ku et al., 2013; Yang and Lin, 2010; Chandra and Bagdi, 2021) also state that students and teachers will have a positive attitude in the education process if they can utilize technology in the digital era. Those who use technology appropriately will be able to survive and be consistent in their education process to achieve success in the longer term.

However, the results of the study of the social climate variable did not contribute to improving teacher achievement. Therefore, the hypothesis proposed in H3 is not accepted or can be said to be rejected. In this study, it was found that teachers who have high motivation and competence are not affected by the conditions of the social climate of the Institution. Most of the teachers who excel

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have targets and frameworks to optimize their potential. This is in line with the results of Maxwell's research in testing the impact of school climate on student academic achievement. Students' perceptions of school climate significantly provide an effect mediated by the psychological identification of the students themselves with the school. Meanwhile, the perceptions of staff and education personnel about school climate do not play an important role. The implications of Maxwell's findings are useful for organizational, social, and educational research which shows that social climate cannot fully influence individual achievement depending on the psychological factors of the individual himself (Maxwell, S. et al., 2017)

In addition, it can be observed by researchers that the Self-Efficacy factor can improve and encourage teachers to be more creative so that they can achieve achievements. This is in line with research (Talsma et al., 2018) Teachers who already have high character and fighting spirit in building the progress of the Institution are not easily influenced by less supportive environmental conditions. They try independently and are actually more creative in developing the competencies they already have. Teachers are involved in social skills in building their madrasah, but teachers are not affected by the social climate of the institution. In the concept of Bandura (1993) states that there are four feelings that can influence individuals who are in a learning environment, namely cognitive, motivational, affective, and selection processes. There are three different levels at which perceived self-efficacy operates as an important contributor to academic development. Students' and teachers' beliefs in their own expertise and abilities are what regulate the learning process and to master academic activities determine their aspirations, motivation levels, and academic achievements. Teachers' beliefs in their abilities or competencies are able to motivate and promote learning so that they can influence the type of learning environment they create and the level of academic progress that will be achieved (Bandura, 1993). Therefore, it is still necessary to conduct research related to other factors such as mental health, emotional stability, readiness in the work environment and others, to further understand their influence on teacher performance and competence.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study have explained that teacher achievement can be influenced by influencer leadership and digital transformation but not by social climate. This study used cross-sectional data which is an observational study by analyzing several variables to test three research hypothesis formulations. The data collected is limited to samples from private madrasahs in Malang Regency, so that the results and implications presented by the author are still limited and cannot be generalized. As a follow-up, further researchers need to include longitudinal data, so that the transition of teacher involvement in forming superior madrasahs is more visible, not only focusing on student achievement. It is also important for further researchers to conduct experimental studies on the influence of different leadership styles and by adding more variables (such as satisfaction, economic strength, self-efficacy, compensation, etc.) that can encourage the achievement of superior madrasahs.

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